

weather parameters and yield showed a positive relationship between total solar radiation during 5-15 d before 50% heading and a negative relationship between number of rainy days 15-30 d before 50% heading. Yield was predicted by these equations:

$$\text{Jaya: } Y = 11.74^{**}X_1 - 308.02^{**}X_2 - 2175$$

(3.91) (2.16)

$$R = 0.73$$

$$\text{IR8: } Y = 10.36^{**}X_1 - 238.80 X_2 - 1720$$

(3.42) (1.65)

$$R = 0.68$$

**Significant at 1% level
*Significant at 5% level

Where, Y = grain yield (kg/ha),
 X_1 = mean solar radiation 5-15 d before 50% heading in mWh/cm² per d, and

X_2 = number of rainy days 15-30 d before 50% heading.

Figures in parentheses are the "t" values of the regression coefficients.

Yield declines were more predominant for crops planted 18 Sep, 3 Oct, and 17 Oct, but yield reductions occurred under adverse weather parameters regardless of planting date. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization HYBRID RICE

Isolation of restorers and maintainers for two Chinese male-sterile lines having wild abortive (WA) cytoplasm

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Pollen from 26 early- and medium-duration rice varieties (8 from IRRI and 18 from India) were crossed with cyto-sterile Zhen Shan 97A and 12 varieties (6 from IRRI and 6 from India) were crossed with cyto-sterile Er-jiu Nan 1A to identify restorers and maintainers of pollen fertility. The two cyto-steriles are of Chinese origin with wild abortive (WA) cytoplasm.

The F₁ hybrids were raised during 1985 rabi in a test cross nursery at Paddy Breeding Station, TNAU. The

Pollen parents classified according to spikelet fertility percentage. TNAU, India.

Cytosterile	Effective restorers >80%	Weak restorers			Weak maintainers			Effective maintainers <5%
		60-80%	40-60%	20-40%	15-20%	10-15%	5-10%	
Zhen Shan 97A	-	-	IR36	IR54 IR56 IR58 IET1722 ASD8 TNAU658 K. Samba	IR40 IR50 IR52 IET4786 A09246 Co41	IR9752 TKM9 BAS370 PTB10 TNAU4372 Co 33 Co 37 Co 39	ADT31 PY2 Co 13 Kanchi	-
Er-jiu-Nan 1A	-	IET6208	IR9698 IET5103	IR19053 IR19058 IR9715 IET13267	IR18599	IR2307 AS19789 IET3630	BPHR5	-

main panicle of each hybrid plant was bagged and spikelet fertility was estimated at harvest. On the basis of spikelet fertility, pollen parents were classified as effective restorers (>80% spikelet fertility); partial or weak restorers (20 to 80% fertility), which is again subdivided into three groups;

weak maintainers (5-20%) and effective maintainers (<5%) (see table).

Stable male-sterile lines MS47A, MS37A, and MS31A are being developed utilizing weak maintainers Co 33, Co 37, and ADT31. A program to identify effective restorers and maintainers is in progress. □

Recurrent selection in rice

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To complement conventional breeding systems and to facilitate hybrid breeding programs, CNPAF and IRAT are synthesizing populations with broad genetic bases. The ability

of these populations to produce good varieties through conventional breeding or to provide good female parents with high prospects for cross pollination for the hybrid program will gradually increase through cyclic application of intermating and selection.

To facilitate intermating, a recessive male sterile gene [from IR36 male sterile (MS)] was introduced. Control of recombination and conservation of

the MS gene are assured by harvesting only open-pollinated seeds from male sterile segregants.

Two populations, one for irrigated rice and one for upland rice, are now ready to be used in conventional breeding systems. The rate of natural outcrossing on male sterile plants is sufficient to guarantee renovation of the populations. An average 165 seeds from male sterile plants of irrigated rice and 26 seeds from upland rice